

INVESTIGATION OF TECHNOLOGICAL AND THERMAL CHARACTERISTICS OF COMPOSITIONS BASED ON WASTE OF POLYVINYL CHLORIDE AND POLYETHYLENE

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Abstract. *The melt fluidity index of the PVC composition with polyethylene was studied and it was determined that with an increase in the PVC content in the polymer composition, the melt fluidity index of the composition increases and at the same time the effective viscosity of polyethylene decreases.*

The thermal characteristics of the PVC composition have been studied, since the loss of mass, the rate of thermal decomposition and the amount of energy consumed for the decomposition of polymers. It was found that with increasing temperature, the mass loss of the PVC composite decreases, and the rate of thermal decomposition and the amount of energy spent on the decomposition of the polymer composite change dramatically, which is explained by a change in the intermolecular interaction of PE macromolecules with PVC.

Keywords: *temperature, mass loss, decomposition rate, spent decomposition energy, polyvinyl chloride, polyethylene.*

Introduction. The global demand for PVC continues to grow, and this trend will continue in the coming years. Not only new areas of application of PVC products, but also a significant expansion of areas contributes to the growth of PVC consumption [1]. Every day, more than one hundred tons of garbage are disposed of all over the planet, some of which is plastic waste. City landfills are littered with bottles, canisters and other polymer objects, the decomposition period of which is equal to a century. Disposal by burning leads to a massive release of toxic poisons into the atmosphere, which has a detrimental effect on the environment. Garbage is the enemy of all living things, as it negatively affects the air, soil and water, and a portion of the released carcinogens is received not only by plants and animals, but also by the human body. The right thing to do to prevent the planet from becoming a landfill is to hand over PVC waste for safe recycling [2].

When processing polyvinyl chloride, a significant amount of waste is generated (up to 50%), which significantly depends on the processing method, type of material, equipment used [3], as well as on the collection of secondary polyethylene (PE) resources. (according to forecasts of Mashpribor-Plastic in the Russian Federation in 2023, 1900 thousand tons)

This figure is growing every year. In Uzbekistan, the amount of such waste is also huge, including waste from greenhouses, pipes, pipelines, hoses, linoleum, equipment components and casings, PVC and PE, the processing of which is an urgent problem, from the point of view of ecology and economics.

Objects and methods of research. The object of the study was polyvinyl chloride, polyethylene waste, obtained, respectively, from used linoleum and secondary polyethylene, which were crushed with a knife crusher. The size of PVC flakes was 5-10 mm, while the bulk density is 250-400 kg / m³.

The PE and PVC composites were prepared in a screw extruder in the temperature range of 140-150 °C with a screw speed of 31 rpm, with a certain PVC:PE ratio. First, they were mechanically mixed, then passed through a screw extruder. The resulting molten mixture was cooled and passed through a granulator. After that, the resulting granules were passed through the extruder 3-4 times under the same conditions to evenly distribute the PVC:PE components.

Derivatographic analysis of the samples was carried out on a DTG-60 Shimadzu Differential Thermal Analyzer in the temperature range of 30-700 °C with a heating rate of 5 deg/min.

Results and discussion

Thermoplastic polymeric materials are processed into products mainly in the molten state. The characteristics of the polymeric material melt are assessed by the melting point (T_m) and melt flow index (MFI).

The melt flow index is understood as the mass of polymers in grams, squeezed out through the capillary of a standard viscometer at a certain temperature, pressure and recalculated for a flow duration of 10 minutes. The melt flow index of PVC and its compositions with PE was determined using a Dynisco LMZ plastometer at a temperature of 190°C, the capillary diameter was 9.1 mm, the load was 107 Pa (GOST 11645). The viscosity of the melt of the polymer compositions was calculated based on the obtained MFI values according to the method [4], the results of which are presented in Table 1.

Analysis of the results of the study (Table 1), the effect of introducing polyvinyl chloride waste into the composition of polyethylene, showed that the value of the melt flow index increases slightly. For example, when introducing 40 and 50 mass. % waste (secondary) PVC melt flow index increases accordingly from 7.92 g/10 min to 9.40 g/10 min. This value for the original PE polymers is 6.5 and for PVC - 18.1 g/10 min.

Table 1

Influence of PVC content on the melt flow index (MFI), melt viscosity, melting point (Melting point) of polyethylene

Indicators	PE	PVC content, wt. %					PVC
	100	30	40	50	60	70	100
MFR, g/10 min	6,5	7,5	7,92	9,40	11,30	16,94	18.1
Viscosity Melt Pa·C·10 ⁻³	923,1	800	757,6	458	392,7	354,2	331,5
Melting point, °C	138	147	155	159	166	178	250

The melt flow index value shows (Fig. 1) that with an increase in the MFI value, the effective viscosity of the melt of the compositions decreases. This is due to a decrease in intermolecular interactions in the polymer macromolecules.

We also determined the melting point of the original polymers (PE, PVC) and their compositions, the results of which are presented in Table 1.

The results of the study show that with an increase in the PVC content in the PE composition, the melting point of PE increases. For example, with a content of 30 and 40 wt. % PVC, the Tm of polyethylene is 147 and 155 ° C, respectively (Table 1).

Fig. 1. Dependence of η_{sp} and MFI of polyethylene on the concentration of polyvinyl chloride

It is known that one of the defining characteristics of the areas of application of polymers is the thermal characteristics of polymer materials. Therefore, we studied the thermal properties of the developed compositions based on polyvinyl chloride and polyethylene waste using the derivatographic method. Fig. 2 shows the results of the analysis of dynamic thermogravimetric curves (DTGA) and differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) of the composition of polyvinyl chloride with polyethylene.

The resulting derivatogram is shown in Fig. 2 and the results of the analysis are given in Table 2. The analysis of the DTGA curve shows that the curve consists mainly of two sigmoids, the process of which occurs in two stages. The first stage occurs in the temperature range from 230 ° C to 360 ° C, while the weight loss is 34.39%. The second stage occurs in the temperature range from 361 ° C to 483 ° C, while the weight loss is 55.20%.

Table 2

Results of the analysis of the DTGA curves of the composition of polyvinyl chloride with polyethylene

	Temperature, °C	PVC content in the composite				
		Weight loss, %				
		30 mass. %	40 mass. %	50 mass. %	60 mass. %	70 mass. %
1	50	0,565	0,965	0,885	0,546	0,946
2	100	1,885	1,985	1,879	1,965	1,265
3	150	9,316	7,876	6,876	7,876	9,976
4	200	11,35	10,35	9,135	11,35	12,35
5	250	17,85	19,85	17,85	23,85	19,32
6	300	23,49	23,95	25,78	26,88	28,78
7	400	38,22	37,82	33,82	41,11	31,51
8	500	57,15	56,87	54,11	53,98	44,95
9	600	67,09	66,54	74,15	72,87	52,17

Decomposition begins at 50°C with increasing temperature, the loss of mass and the rate of decomposition of the polymer increase. Intensive decomposition of the polymer mainly occurs after 300°C and reaches a maximum at 400°C, with the loss of mass being 23.49 mass% and

38.22%, respectively. Comparison of the results of the study in Table 2 show that when polyvinyl chloride waste is introduced into the PE composition, the thermal stability of the composition decreases.

Fig. 2. Derivatogram of polyvinyl chloride with polyethylene PVC:PE compositions. 30:70 (1-DTGA curve; 2-DSC curve)

For example, at a temperature of 300 °C and a concentration of 30; 40; 50; 60 and 70 wt.% of polyvinyl chloride in the PE composition, the weight loss is 23.49; 23.95; 25.78; 26.88; and 28.78 wt.%, respectively.

One of the parameters for assessing the thermal stability of polymers is determining the rate of decomposition. Therefore, the decomposition rates of PVC with polyethylene compositions in various concentrations were determined, the results of which are given in Table 3.

An analysis of the study results (Table 3) shows that with an increase in the concentration of polyvinyl chloride, the thermal stability of PE changes extremely. This is obviously due to a slight increase in the intermolecular interaction of PE macromolecules with PVC.

Fig. 2. Derivatogram of polyvinyl chloride compositions with polyethylene PVC:PE. 70:30 (1-DTGA curve; 2-DSC curve);

Analysis of the decomposition rate of the composition based on PVC and PE (Table 3) shows that the decomposition rate occurs in the temperature ranges from 50 °C to 600 °C at a rate of 0.142 - 1.265 mg / min. From the analysis of the research results it is evident that decomposition mainly occurs at a high rate at 400 °C - 2.499 mg / min.

Table 3

**Results of the decomposition rate of polyvinyl chloride compositions with polyethylene
PVC:PE**

№	Temperature, °C	Decomposition rate, mg/min PVC content in the composite				
		30 mass. %	40 mass. %	50 mass. %	60 mass.%	70 mass.%
1	50	0,142	0,145	0,224	0,425	0,365
2	100	0,465	0,412	0,451	0,554	0,552
3	150	0,585	0,552	0,651	0,412	0,432
4	200	0,125	1,178	1,478	2,178	2,198
5	250	0,147	2,178	2,778	3,178	3,114
6	300	0,455	2,455	2,655	3,214	3,296
7	400	2,499	3,499	3,299	3,299	3,235
8	500	2,125	3,125	3,325	3,554	3,325
9	600	1,265	3,265	3,665	3,745	3,410

Another of the main criteria for the thermal characteristics of PVC compositions is the amount of energy expended ($\mu V \cdot s/mg$) for the decomposition of polymeric materials.

Therefore, the compositions of polyvinyl chloride with polyethylene were studied by differential scanning calorimetry using DSC curves, the results of which are given in Table 4.

Table 4

**Results of the amount of energy expended (DSC) for polyvinyl chloride with polyethylene
(PVC:PE) compositions**

№	Temperature, °C	Amount of energy expended ($\mu V \cdot s/mg$) PVC content in the composite				
		30,0 mass. %	40,0 mass. %	50,0 mass. %	60,0 mass. %	70%
1	50	1,54	1,54	1,11	1,41	1,41
2	100	2,62	2,62	2,23	2,20	2,20
3	150	2,32	2,32	2,45	2,54	2,54
4	200	3,65	3,65	3,22	3,54	3,54
5	250	1,11	4,11	4,23	4,98	4,98
6	300	2,55	4,54	4,12	4,54	4,55
7	400	1,59	5,55	5,59	5,63	5,68
8	500	1,32	5,32	5,55	5,32	5,32
9	600	1,66	2,66	2,87	2,58	2,54
10	700	1,32	1,32	1,65	1,54	1,99
11	800	1,45	1,45	1,77	1,21	1,33

Analysis of the research results (Table 4) in Fig. 2 shows that for PVC and compositions based on them, the amount of energy expended ($\mu V \cdot s/mg$) for the decomposition of polymers changes extremely.

With an increase in the content of polyvinyl chloride, the amount of energy expended increases. For example, for a composition containing 30; 40.0; 50; 60; and 70 wt.% polyvinyl

chloride, the amount of energy expended for the decomposition of polymer compositions with an increase in the content of the latter at 400 ° C is 1.59; 5.55; 5.59; 5.63; and 5.68 μV·s/mg, respectively.

Comparison of the tabular values of the amount of energy spent for the decomposition of polyvinyl chloride compositions (Table 4) shows that most energy is spent mainly in the temperature range of 300-400 ° C, with a PVC concentration of 70%, which is in the range of 4.55-5.68 μV·s/mg, respectively.

Also, for a comparative assessment of the thermal stability of a polyvinyl chloride composition with polyethylene, data on temperature are presented (Table 5). Analysis of the research results shows that with an increase in the content of polyvinyl chloride, the temperature of the onset of decomposition of polyethylene increases. For example, the temperature of the onset of decomposition of compositions containing 30; 40; 50; 60 and 70, mass.% is 103; 105; 107; 111 and 114 ° C, respectively.

Table 5

Results of thermal stability of polyvinyl chloride compositions with secondary polyethylene

Sample	Decomposition temperature, °C				Weight loss at a certain temperature, %	
	T ₀	T ₁₀	T ₂₀	T ₅₀	T ₄₀₀	T ₆₀₀
PVC (original)	98	144	189	512	34,45	57,25
PVC + PE 30:70	103	167	229	544	38,22	67,09
PVC + PE 40:60	105	174	235	559	37,82	66,54
PVC + PE 50:50	107	184	239	574	33,82	65,15
PVC + PE 60:40	111	191	244	581	32,11	64,87
PVC + PE70:30	114	201	250	590	31,51	63,17

Comparison of the results of tabular values of thermal stability of composites at a ratio of 30:70 PVC and PE at T₄₀₀ ° C and T₆₀₀ ° C, the weight loss is the highest 38.22 and 67.09, respectively. This is due to the intermolecular interaction of PE macromolecules with PVC.

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